

PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF DENTAL ANOMALIES IN CHILDREN SUFFERING FROM SCOLIOSIS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8388874>

Abstract

To develop a rational method for the treatment of dentoalveolar anomalies complicated by periodontal diseases, aimed at achieving stable treatment results, depending on the density of bone tissue in patients with scoliosis.

Dental anomalies were treated in children suffering from scoliosis of various localizations with signs of osteopenic syndrome. The patients were divided into four groups of 24 children - three main groups and a comparison group. A method for drug correction of osteopenic conditions of the alveolar process has been developed and applied.

Keywords: scoliosis, osteopenic syndrome.

Dental anomalies are a factor contributing to the occurrence of periodontal diseases and worsening their course. In the presence of dental anomalies, the hygienic condition of the oral cavity deteriorates, microcirculation is disrupted, and an inadequate load on periodontal tissue may be observed. Therefore, orthodontic intervention is necessary in the complex treatment of periodontal diseases [1, 4, 5]. It is known that the restructuring of weakened periodontal tissues during orthodontic treatment differs from that observed with intact periodontium, therefore, there is a sharply expressed resorption of the internal surfaces of the alveolar sockets and insufficient compensatory layering of new bone during the retention period. During orthodontic treatment, peeling of epithelial cells in the oral mucosa increases, blood vessels in the connective tissue are compressed, the trophism of epithelial tissues, protective processes and enzymatic balance are disrupted, and the nature of reflex reactions changes. As a result of the mechanical action of the device, the proliferation of cells in the basal layer of the epithelium is delayed, which is partially compensated by the high ability to regenerate the oral mucosa [2, 3]. With high efficiency, such methods have the ability to negatively influence the condition of periodontal tissues [3], the hygienic condition of the oral cavity [7], and promote the demineralization of tooth enamel [6]. Therefore, there is an active search for means of prevention, and in many cases, treatment of periodontal diseases that may occur during orthodontic treatment. tissue in patients with scoliosis. Materials and methods of research To achieve this goal, 96 patients aged 12 to 17 years who sought orthodontic care were examined. All examined patients were treated for dental crowding. When studying diagnostic models of jaws, anomalies in the size of the teeth and dentition, the location of the teeth, and the shape of the dentition were determined. A violation of the rela-

tionship of the dentition in three mutually perpendicular directions was revealed. Four groups were formed. The first group (comparison) – 24 practically healthy patients (9 boys and 15 girls, average age ($M \pm m$) – 14.9 ± 0.2 years). Six people had a shortened tongue frenulum. Periodontal tissues are intact. Hygiene level is good. The second group included 24 patients with scoliosis (three patients had grade III–IV scoliosis, grade II – 5 patients, grade I – 16 patients). Among them there were 6 boys and 18 girls, the average age was 14.8 ± 0.2 years. Ten patients had a shortened frenulum of the tongue. The patients had chronic catarrhal gingivitis, predominantly of a generalized form. The level of hygiene is satisfactory. All of them received traditional orthodontic treatment and professional oral hygiene. The third group - 24 patients with scoliosis (III-IV degree of scoliosis had 4 patients, II - 4 patients, I - 16 patients). Among them there were 7 boys and 17 girls, the average age was 14.0 ± 0.3 years. The patients had chronic catarrhal gingivitis, predominantly of a generalized form. The level of hygiene is unsatisfactory. Twelve patients had functional disorders, namely, oral or mixed breathing was observed, which was accompanied by a decrease in the tone of the orbicularis oris muscle. Eight patients underwent plastic surgery of a shortened lingual frenulum. In addition to the above-mentioned treatment, before orthodontic treatment, patients received applications of the Cholisal gel on the gums; in the presence of functional disorders, myogymnastics was performed; after treatment, the drug Calcium-D3Nycomed was prescribed.

The fourth group included 24 patients with scoliosis (three patients had grade III-IV scoliosis, grade II – 5 patients, stage I – 16 patients). Among them there were 7 boys and 17 girls, the average age was 14.2 ± 0.3 years. The patients had chronic catarrhal gingivitis, predominantly of a generalized form. The level of hygiene

is unsatisfactory. Sixteen patients had functional disorders. They had oral or mixed breathing and decreased tone of the orbicularis oris muscle. Nine people underwent plastic surgery of a shortened lingual frenulum. with vitamin C" 0.25 mg, one tablet twice a day after meals, then use the drug "Calcium-D3Nycomed" one tablet twice a day after meals for a month. Ultraphonophoresis with a 5% oil solution of acetate-tocopherol was prescribed locally, which was carried out alternately with irradiation of the alveolar process with the light of a helium-neon laser. (13.5±3.5%) patients experienced a narrowing of the second stage dentition. It should be noted that the identified four groups of patients were compared by age ($p > 0.10$), gender ($p > 0.30$), degree of narrowing of the dentition ($p > 0.60$), and the groups of patients with scoliosis were compared by the degree of scoliosis ($p > 0.80$). Orthodontic treatment of crowded teeth was carried out in all patients using non-removable equipment, namely, braces. During the retention period, removable retention devices were used. Due to various circumstances, not all patients responded to the request to appear for examination - 74 people out of 96 previously treated (77.1%). There were no recurrences of dental anomalies in patients of the first group. Hygiene index – 1.36±0.05 is regarded as good. In patients of the second group, partial relapses of dentoalveolar anomalies were observed in four people (22.2±9.8%), relapse of chronic catarrhal gingivitis - in 16 people (88.9±7.4%). RMA index 13.62± 1.48% indicates a mild form of this disease, a hygiene index of 2.09±0.07 indicates an unsatisfactory state of oral hygiene. relapses of chronic catarrhal gingivitis - in 5 (29.4±11.1%), the hygienic index is satisfactory, the PMA index of 3.57±1.44% indicates a mild localized form of this disease. In patients of the fourth group, no recurrence of dentoalveolar anomalies was detected; relapse of gingivitis occurred in only two people (10.5±7.0%), an easily localized form of the disease (PMA index –1.50±1.05%), hygienic index 1, 54±0.08 indicates a satisfactory state of hygiene. Assessing the long-term results, we can say that relapses of dentoalveolar anomalies did not occur in practically healthy patients and patients with scoliosis from the fourth group, which indicates the effectiveness of our proposed treatment regimen. In patients of the second group, the number of relapses of dentoalveolar anomalies was significantly higher than in patients of the first and fourth groups ($p < 0.05$ by two-sided Fisher test), which may indicate imperfection of the processes of bone tissue remodeling in patients of the second group. The third group occupied an intermediate position between all groups ($p > 0.20$ for all comparisons with other groups). Relapses of chronic catarrhal gingivitis were observed in patients of all three groups with scoliosis, but the lowest was in patients of the fourth group -10.5±7.0%, the highest in patients of the second group -88.9±7.4% ($p < 0.001$ compared to other groups 2 and Fisher closures). The hygiene index was also the worst in patients

of the second group - 2.09 ± 0.07, which is regarded as "unsatisfactory" ($p < 0.01$ compared with other groups according to Duncan's criterion). The above-mentioned results indicate that the treatment regimen we proposed in the fourth group turned out to be the most successful, which made it possible to bring the final results of treatment of patients with osteopenia closer to those of practically healthy patients. Assessing the overall effectiveness of treatment, it should be noted that chronic catarrhal gingivitis had relapses in only 23 people out of all those treated - 7431.1±5.4%, and a decrease in the PMA index from 24.54±1.7 to 4.53± 0.83% ($p < 0.001$) that mild localized forms of this disease predominate. Therefore, we can conclude that orthodontic treatment has a fairly positive effect on the condition of periodontal tissues, and it can be used to exclude this link in the pathogenesis of periodontal diseases.

conclusions

Orthodontic treatment in combination with the treatment and prophylactic complex we have developed has a positive effect on the condition of periodontal tissues, and it can be used to eliminate this link in the pathogenesis of periodontal tissue diseases.

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